

Table S2. The Association between selected SNPs and breast cancer risk in East Asian women.

Chr	Position	SNP	gene	EA ^a	OA ^a	East Asian women				European women	
						EA ^a	Number	beta	se	One-sided P	beta (95 % CI) ^b
44 SNPs used for the construction of the polygenic genetic score											
1	10566215	rs616488	PEX14	A	G	0.70	23564	0.070	0.020	2.96E-04	0.058(0.038-0.077)
1	121280613	rs11249433	EMBP1	G	A	0.08	23566	0.088	0.052	4.51E-02	0.093(0.073-0.112)
1	203766331	rs4951011	ZC3H11A	G	A	0.31	23567	0.056	0.021	3.47E-03	0.034(0.006-0.063)
2	19320803	rs12710696	MIR4757	T	C	0.33	18044	0.048	0.023	1.91E-02	0.039(0.019-0.058)
2	121245122	rs4849887	LOC84931	C	T	0.80	23567	0.065	0.024	2.97E-03	0.100(0.068-0.132)
2	202143928	rs10931936	CASP8	T	C	0.29	18045	0.053	0.024	1.30E-02	0.042(0.021-0.062)
2	217905832	rs13387042	TNP1	A	G	0.12	23567	0.056	0.029	2.87E-02	0.132(0.114-0.151)
2	218296508	rs16857609	DIRC3	T	C	0.60	23563	0.084	0.019	6.80E-06	0.079(0.058-0.100)
3	27416013	rs4973768	SLC4A7	T	C	0.21	23564	0.107	0.023	1.79E-06	0.094(0.075-0.113)
3	30682939	rs12493607	GFBR2	C	G	0.67	18044	0.050	0.023	1.62E-02	0.054(0.035-0.073)
4	175846426	rs6828523	ADAM29	C	A	0.75	18044	0.058	0.025	9.25E-03	0.108(0.079-0.137)
5	1279790	rs10069690	TERT	T	C	0.20	23562	0.065	0.026	6.40E-03	0.059(0.038-0.080)
5	44706498	rs10941679	MRPS30	G	A	0.50	18045	0.067	0.022	1.26E-03	0.120(0.099-0.141)
5	56031884	rs889312	MAP3K1	C	A	0.55	23564	0.038	0.019	2.22E-02	0.115(0.095-0.136)
5	90732225	rs10474352	LOC100129716	C	T	0.55	23567	0.077	0.020	5.60E-05	0.058(0.027-0.088)
5	158244083	rs1432679	EBF1	C	T	0.65	23567	0.068	0.020	3.26E-04	0.070(0.051-0.089)
6	149608874	rs9485372	TAB2	G	A	0.58	18045	0.128	0.022	3.96E-09	0.048(0.024-0.073)
6	151948366	rs2046210	C6orf97	A	G	0.38	23567	0.237	0.020	0.00E+00	0.078(0.058-0.097)
8	29509616	rs9693444	C8orf75	A	C	0.29	23566	0.074	0.021	1.80E-04	0.068(0.048-0.087)
8	76230301	rs6472903	HNF4G	T	G	0.96	23567	0.118	0.049	7.80E-03	0.095(0.070-0.120)
8	128387852	rs1562430	POU5F1B	T	C	0.83	23567	0.067	0.025	3.85E-03	0.106(0.087-0.125)
9	22062134	rs1011970	CDKN2B-AS1	T	G	0.09	23566	0.063	0.033	2.66E-02	0.054(0.029-0.079)
9	110306115	rs10759243	9q31.2	A	C	0.44	18045	0.057	0.022	4.36E-03	0.048(0.028-0.069)
10	64251977	rs10822013	ZNF365	T	C	0.50	23567	0.075	0.019	3.48E-05	0.063(0.044-0.082)
10	80841148	rs704010	ZMIZ1	T	C	0.32	23564	0.063	0.020	9.35E-04	0.081(0.062-0.100)

10	123093901	rs11199914	10q26.12	C	T	0.62	18045	0.042	0.022	3.07E-02	0.051(0.031-0.071)
10	123337335	rs2981579	FGFR2	A	G	0.46	23567	0.151	0.019	1.34E-15	0.236(0.217-0.255)
11	1941946	rs909116	TNNT3	T	C	0.39	23555	0.075	0.020	1.09E-04	0.070(0.051-0.089)
11	69328764	rs614367	CCND1	T	C	0.01	23565	0.249	0.094	4.02E-03	0.194(0.169-0.220)
11	129473690	rs7107217	BARX2	C	A	0.37	18040	0.095	0.023	1.25E-05	0.045(0.026-0.063)
12	14413931	rs12422552	ATF7IP	C	G	0.29	18043	0.054	0.024	1.36E-02	0.042(0.021-0.063)
12	28155080	rs10771399	PTHLH	A	G	0.82	23567	0.112	0.024	2.09E-06	0.159(0.130-0.189)
12	96027759	rs17356907	NTN4	A	G	0.76	23567	0.063	0.022	2.21E-03	0.093(0.073-0.114)
12	115836522	rs1292011	MED13L	A	G	0.75	23566	0.117	0.022	4.95E-08	0.084(0.065-0.103)
14	37132769	rs2236007	PAX9	G	A	0.72	23561	0.071	0.021	4.22E-04	0.076(0.053-0.099)
14	91841069	rs941764	CCDC88C	G	A	0.15	23565	0.062	0.027	9.55E-03	0.063(0.043-0.082)
15	91512067	rs2290203	PRC1	G	A	0.51	18045	0.081	0.022	8.15E-05	0.039(0.015-0.062)
16	52586341	rs3803662	LOC643714	A	G	0.63	23565	0.129	0.020	2.64E-11	0.215(0.194-0.236)
16	52599188	rs4784227	LOC643714	T	C	0.27	23567	0.209	0.022	0.00E+00	0.227(0.206-0.249)
16	53855291	rs11075995	FTO	A	T	0.31	18044	0.071	0.024	1.19E-03	0.043(0.021-0.065)
18	24337424	rs527616	LOC728606	G	C	0.71	23566	0.042	0.021	2.27E-02	0.054(0.035-0.073)
19	17394124	rs2363956	ANKLE1	T	G	0.68	23562	0.057	0.021	2.88E-03	0.027(0.008-0.045)
19	18571141	rs4808801	ELL	A	G	0.75	23561	0.055	0.022	5.65E-03	0.078(0.058-0.098)
22	39358037	rs12628403	APOBEC3A	C	A	0.34	23561	0.108	0.024	4.56E-06	0.051(0.011-0.091)

Other SNPs

1	114448389	rs11552449	DCLRE1B	T	C	0.60	23566	0.018	0.020	1.88E-01	0.066(0.041-0.091)
1	202187176	rs6678914	LGR6	G	A	0.77	18044	0.012	0.026	3.19E-01	0.009(-0.010-0.028)
1	204518842	rs4245739	MDM4	C	A	0.05	18043	-0.037	0.051	7.67E-01	0.033(0.012-0.054)
2	172972971	rs2016394	METAP1D	G	A	0.79	18045	0.016	0.028	2.87E-01	0.044(0.025-0.062)
2	174212894	rs1550623	CDCA7	A	G	0.98	18040	0.140	0.092	6.35E-02	0.060(0.034-0.086)
2	202149589	rs1045485	CASP8	G	C	1.00	23565	-0.178	0.303	7.21E-01	0.030(0.002-0.058)
3	4742276	rs6762644	ITPR1/EGOT	G	A	0.09	23566	0.039	0.034	1.22E-01	0.066(0.047-0.085)
4	106084778	rs9790517	TET2	T	C	0.60	18043	0.010	0.022	3.24E-01	0.057(0.035-0.080)
5	44899885	rs9790879	MRPS30	T	C	0.44	18042	-0.041	0.022	9.69E-01	0.085(0.066-0.104)
5	58184061	rs10472076	RAB3C	C	T	0.26	23566	0.011	0.022	2.99E-01	0.043(0.023-0.062)
5	58337481	rs1353747	PDE4D	T	G	1.00	18045	0.204	0.187	1.38E-01	0.074(0.042-0.106)

6	1318878	rs11242675	FOXQ1	T	C	0.45	23566	-0.019	0.019	8.47E-01	0.038(0.019-0.058)
6	13722523	rs204247	RANBP9	G	A	0.60	23566	0.023	0.019	1.16E-01	0.047(0.028-0.066)
6	82193109	rs17530068	FAM46A	C	T	0.22	23567	0.031	0.023	8.35E-02	0.054(0.032-0.076)
6	151914113	rs3757318	C6orf97	A	G	0.28	23566	0.167	0.022	4.11E-15	0.146(0.110-0.181)
7	144074929	rs720475	ARHGEF5/NOBO	G	A	0.96	18045	0.025	0.059	3.36E-01	0.059(0.037-0.081)
8	76417937	rs2943559	HNF4G	G	A	0.09	18045	-0.038	0.039	8.38E-01	0.128(0.093-0.163)
8	128355618	rs13281615	POU5F1B	G	A	0.52	23429	0.021	0.019	1.38E-01	0.093(0.074-0.112)
8	129194641	rs11780156	MIR1208	T	C	0.21	18045	-0.026	0.026	8.38E-01	0.068(0.043-0.093)
9	110888478	rs865686	9q31	T	G	0.93	23567	0.056	0.037	6.65E-02	0.103(0.084-0.123)
10	5886734	rs2380205	ANKRD16	C	T	0.88	18042	0.016	0.033	3.14E-01	0.013(-0.006-0.032)
10	22032942	rs7072776	MLLT10/DNAJ	A	G	0.06	23567	0.002	0.045	4.81E-01	0.062(0.042-0.083)
10	22315843	rs11814448	DNAJC1	C	A	0.01	23567	0.064	0.096	2.53E-01	0.238(0.174-0.301)
10	64278682	rs10995190	ZNF365	G	A	0.98	23567	-0.017	0.065	6.02E-01	0.149(0.123-0.175)
10	114773927	rs7904519	TCF7L2	G	A	0.07	23566	0.060	0.052	1.24E-01	0.056(0.037-0.075)
10	123352317	rs2981582	FGFR2	A	G	0.33	23565	0.115	0.020	3.87E-09	0.227(0.208-0.246)
11	1909006	rs3817198	LSP1	C	T	0.14	23565	0.084	0.027	1.05E-03	0.066(0.046-0.087)
11	65583066	rs3903072	OVOL1	G	T	0.79	18045	0.046	0.027	4.26E-02	0.054(0.035-0.073)
11	129461171	rs11820646	BARX2	C	T	0.54	23565	0.041	0.019	1.78E-02	0.051(0.032-0.070)
13	32972626	rs11571833	BRCA2	T	A	0.00	23566	0.496	0.538	1.79E-01	0.246(0.149-0.343)
14	68660428	rs2588809	RAD51L1	T	C	0.03	23567	0.053	0.062	1.94E-01	0.075(0.050-0.101)
14	69034682	rs999737	RAD51B	C	T	1.00	23566	-0.081	0.154	7.01E-01	0.084(0.061-0.106)
14	69039588	rs8009944	RAD51B	C	A	0.73	18044	0.030	0.025	1.10E-01	0.035(0.014-0.056)
16	52548037	rs12443621	TOX3	G	A	0.57	18045	0.013	0.022	2.84E-01	0.120(0.101-0.139)
16	53813367	rs17817449	MIR1972	T	G	0.86	23566	0.044	0.027	5.30E-02	0.072(0.053-0.091)
16	80650805	rs13329835	CDYL2	G	A	0.05	23567	0.058	0.042	8.55E-02	0.078(0.056-0.101)
17	53056471	rs6504950	STXBP4/COX1	G	A	0.91	18045	-0.010	0.038	6.00E-01	0.062(0.041-0.083)
18	24570667	rs1436904	CHST9	T	G	0.54	23564	0.029	0.019	6.30E-02	0.049(0.030-0.068)
19	17389704	rs8170	BABAM1	A	G	0.01	23566	0.121	0.170	2.38E-01	0.040(0.016-0.063)
19	44286513	rs3760982	KCNN4/ZNF28	A	G	0.16	23567	-0.017	0.026	7.45E-01	0.053(0.034-0.071)
20	32588095	rs2284378	RALY	T	C	0.18	18045	-0.015	0.028	7.02E-01	0.017(-0.003-0.037)
21	16520832	rs2823093	NRIP1	G	A	0.96	18045	0.068	0.055	1.09E-01	0.075(0.054-0.097)

22	29621477	rs132390	EMID1/RHBDD3	C	T	0.00	18045	0.038	0.271	4.44E-01	0.123(0.074-0.172)
22	40876234	rs6001930	MKL1	C	T	0.25	23566	0.022	0.022	1.55E-01	0.117(0.088-0.147)

^a Abbreviations: EA, effect allele; OA, other allele; EAF, effect allele frequency.

^b The association, beta and their 95% confidence intervals, between the selected SNPs and breast cancer risk, estimated from 91,767 women of European ancestry participating in the Breast Cancer Association Consortium [Mavaddat N, Pharoah P, Michailidou K. Prediction of breast cancer risk based on profiling with common genetic variants. *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* 2015;107(5) djv036].